

Synthesis of 6-Substituted Azo-5,7-Dimethyl (or Diphenyl) 2,3-Dihydro-6H-1,4-Diazepines

RAMAN GROVER and B. C. JOSHI*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, (India)

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Diazonium salts of aniline and substituted sulphanilamides were reacted with 2, 4-pentadione and dibenzoylmethane. The intermediates were identified as 3-substituted azo-2,4-pentadiones (IA, IIIA, VA and VIIA) and substituted azo dibenzoylmethane (IIA, IVA, VIA and VIIIA). On reacting IA-VIIIA with 1, 2-diaminoethane 6-substituted azo-5,7-dimethyl (or diphenyl)-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepines (IB-VIIIB) were obtained. The structures to IA-VIIIA and IB-VIIIB were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral studies.

DIAZEPINES and its related compounds are potent CNS drugs used as tranquiliser, muscle relaxant psychosedative anticonvulsant, etc.¹⁻⁴. The present work deals with the syntheses of a new class of compounds in which various substituted azo compounds were attached to 1,4-diazepine moiety at position 6 in order to combine the bacterostatic⁵ and CNS activity in a single molecule. For this purpose, a start was made by diazotising aniline and substituted sulphanilamides separately and condensing diazonium salts with the diketones (viz. 2, 4-pentadione and dibenzoylmethane). After having established the structures, the azo compounds (IA-VIIIA) were refluxed for 8-10 hr. with 1, 2-diaminoethane in absolute ethanol. The reaction mixtures were kept in freeze overnight when solid separated out. Repeated crystallisation resulted in pure sample of the corresponding diazepine derivatives (IB-VIIIB).

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60D model using TMS as internal reference.

3-(Guanidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-2,4-Pentadione (IIIA)

To an ice cold solution of acetylacetone (1.0 g., 0.01M) in acetone containing anhy. CH_3COONa (60.0 g) a diazotised solution of sulphaguanidine (2.14 g., 0.01M; diazotized with dil HCl and NaNO_2 at 0-5°) was gradually added at 0-5° with constant stirring. The stirring was further continued for 15 min and the azo compound was precipitated by the addition of cold H_2O . The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with H_2O and dried. The crude product was crystallised from glacial CH_3COOH (IIIA, m.p. 258°; yield 2.14 g., 65.87%).

I and I B,	R = C ₆ H ₅	R ₁ = CH ₃
IIA and II B,	R = C ₆ H ₅ NH	R ₁ = C ₆ H ₅
IIIA and III B	R = H ₂ N-C-NH-SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	R ₁ = CH ₃
IVA and IV B	R = H ₂ N-C-NH-SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	R ₁ = C ₆ H ₅
VA and V B	R = C ₆ H ₄ -NH-SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	R ₁ = CH ₃
VIA and VI B	R = C ₆ H ₄ -NH-SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	R ₁ = C ₆ H ₅
VIIA and VII B	R = C ₆ H ₄ -NH-SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	R ₁ = CH ₃
VIIIA and VIII B	R = C ₆ H ₄ -NH-SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	R ₁ = C ₆ H ₅

Analysis

Found : C, 44.08 ; H, 4.49 ; N, 21.78%
Calcd. for : C₁₂H₁₅O₄N₅S
C, 44.31 ; H, 4.62 ; N, 21.54%.

6-(Guanidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-Dimethyl-2,3-Dihydro 6H-1,4-Diazepine (IIIB)

To IIIA (1.6250 g., 0.005M) taken in absolute C₂H₅OH (10 ml) 1, 2-diaminoethane (1.5 g.,

TABLE-1

Compound Number	Molecular Formula	Melting Point	Yield %	Analysis %					
				Calculated			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
IA	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	90°	69.61	64.71	5.88	13.73	64.40	6.08	13.91
IIA	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	150°	67.00	76.83	4.88	8.54	76.47	5.12	8.81
IIIA	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	258°	66.77	44.31	4.62	21.54	44.08	4.49	21.78
IVA	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	240°	66.82	58.80	4.23	15.59	59.12	4.40	15.38
VA	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	235°	69.44	53.33	4.44	15.55	53.10	4.72	15.25
VIA	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	230°	64.88	64.46	4.13	11.57	64.26	4.32	11.75
VIIA	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	210°	66.48	49.86	4.16	19.39	49.58	4.32	19.62
VIIIA	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	221°	64.33	61.86	3.91	14.43	62.10	3.68	14.84

TABLE-2

Compound Number	Molecular Formula	Melting Point	Yield %	Analysis %					
				Calculated			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
IB	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄	185°	64.91	68.42	7.02	24.56	68.68	6.80	24.33
IIB	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄	205°	59.66	78.41	5.68	15.91	78.71	5.43	15.72
IIIB	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	295°	63.04	48.14	5.44	28.08	48.48	5.24	27.80
IVB	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	301°	61.31	60.89	4.86	20.72	61.17	4.68	20.46
VB	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	305°	63.80	56.25	5.21	21.88	55.94	5.39	22.12
VIB	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	290°	61.02	66.14	4.72	16.54	65.86	4.93	16.52
VIIIB	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	248°	62.34	52.99	4.94	24.45	52.69	5.15	25.66
VIIIB	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	261°	59.92	63.65	4.52	19.25	63.32	4.72	19.47

0.025M) was added with shaking and cooling. The contents were refluxed for 8 hr. and cooled to room temperature. The reaction mixture was kept in freeze overnight when orange coloured solid settled. The crude product was crystallised from C₂H₅OH (IIIB, m.p. 295°, yield 1.10 g., 63.04%).

Analysis

Found : C, 48.48 ; H, 5.24 ; N, 27.80%

Calcd. for : C₁₄H₁₉O₂N₂S
C, 48.14 ; H, 5.44 ; N, 28.08%

Similarly IB, IIB, IVB-VIIIB were prepared. The melting points, yields and elemental analyses of these compounds are compiled in Table 2.

Structural Elucidation

Compound IA-VIIIA : On the basis of elemental analyses the molecular formulae to IA-VIIIA were suggested as shown in Table 1.

In the Ir spectra¹ of IA-VIIIA, the presence of carbonyl group was established on the basis of characteristic peaks at 1670-1650 cm⁻¹ and 1265-1260 cm⁻¹. In the Ir spectra of IA-VIIIA the characteristic absorption bands at 1570 cm⁻¹, 1406 ± 4 cm⁻¹ were assigned to N=N group in these molecules. The presence of sulphonamide group in IIIA-VIIIA was established by the characteristic band in the vicinity of 1380 cm⁻¹.

In the Nmr spectra studies (c.f. Table 3) the presence of six protons for two methyl groups in IA,

TABLE-3

(Nmr spectra - Chemical shifts expressed in δ ppm)

Compound Number	NH-protons δ(DMSO)	Aromatic protons	-C-CH ₃ -protons
IA	-	7.0-7.7 5H	2.4(d) 6H
IIA	-	6.6-7.8 15H	-
IIIA	9.2(b) 4H	6.7-8.2 4H	2.4-2.5(d) 6H
IVA	9.2(b) 4H	6.7-8.2 14H	-
VA	9.1-9.3(b) 1H	6.7-8.2 8H	2.4-2.5(d) 6H
VIA	9.1-9.3(b) 1H	6.7-8.2 18H	-
VIIA	9.1-9.3(b) 1H	6.7-8.2 7H	2.4-2.5(d) 6H
VIIIA	9.1-9.3(b) 1H	6.7-8.2 17H	-

b=broad ; d=doublet.

IIIA, VA and VIIA were established on the basis of the signal as doublet in the region δ2.4-δ2.5. The signals as complicated pattern for the aromatic protons in the Nmr of IA-VIIIA were observed in the range of δ6.6-δ8.2. The signal for the proton as -CH was, however, not found in any of these Nmr spectra, indicating thereby the existence of these compounds in enolic form in acidic medium. The presence of four protons attached to nitrogens in

IIIa with and IVa were established on the basis of a broad signal in the vicinity of $\delta 9.2$ while the signal for one proton attached to nitrogen in VA-VIIIa was also found in the range of $\delta 9.1$ - $\delta 9.3$

On the basis of these observations the structures the IA-VIIIa were assigned as :

3-(Phenylazo)-2,4-pentadione to IA, (Phenylazo)-dibenzoylmethane to IIA, 3-(guanidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-2,4-pentadione to IIIa, (guanidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)dibenzoylmethane to IVA, 3-(pyridylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-2,4-pentadione to VA, (pyridylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)dibenzoylmethane to VIA, 3-(pyrimidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-2,4-pentadione to VIIa and (pyrimidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)dibenzoylmethane to VIIIa.

Compound IB-VIIIb

On the basis of elemental analyses the molecular formulae to IB-VIIIb were suggested as shown in Table 2.

Comparison of the Ir spectra of IB-VIIIb with that of the corresponding azo derivatives of diketones (IA-VIIIb), indicated the absence of characteristic absorption bands at 1670 - 1650 cm^{-1} and 1265 - 1260 cm^{-1} , position assigned for carbonyl group in IA-VIIIa, concluding thereby that the carbonyl groups of IA-VIIIa reacted with 1,2-diaminoethane.

The Nmr spectra of IB-IIIb, VB and VIIB (c.f. Table 4) indicated the presence of the signal for six protons at $\delta 2.8$, a broad signal for four protons in

the range of $\delta 4.1$ - $\delta 4.3$, a signal as a bump for a proton in the range of $\delta 3.3$ - $\delta 3.7$ and the signals as a complicated pattern for aromatic protons in the range of $\delta 6.6$ - $\delta 8.4$. The signal for proton attached to nitrogen was observed in the range of $\delta 9.2$ - $\delta 9.9$ in the Nmr spectra of IIIB, VB and VIIB. In the Nmr spectra of IIB, IVB, VIB and VIIIb (c. f. Table 4) indicated the presence of one methine proton in the range of $\delta 3.5$ - $\delta 3.7$, four protons, i.e., two $-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-$ groups in the region $\delta 4.2$ - $\delta 4.4$ and aromatic protons in the region $\delta 6.3$ - $\delta 8.5$. The proton attached to the nitrogen was found to be present in the region $\delta 9.2$ - $\delta 9.9$ in the Nmr spectra of IVB, VIIB and VIIIb.

On the basis of these observations the structures to IB-VIIIb were assigned as 6-(phenylazo)-5,7-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to IB, 6-(phenylazo)-5,7-diphenyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to IIB, 6-(guanidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to IIIB, 6-(guanidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-diphenyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to IVB, 6-(pyridylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to VB, 6-(pyridylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-diphenyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to VIB, 6-(pyrimidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to VIIB and 6-(pyrimidylsulphonamidobenzeneazo)-5,7-diphenyl-2,3-dihydro-6H-1,4-diazepine to VIIIb.

TABLE-4

Compound number	(Nmr spectra—Chemical shifts expressed in δ ppm)				
	-NH protons δ (DMSO)	Aromatic protons	=N-CH ₂ protons	CH protons	=C-CH ₃ protons
IB	-	7.2-7.8 5H	4.2(b) 4H	3.3(b) 1H	2.8(s) 6H
IIB	-	6.3-7.8 15H	4.3(b) 4H	3.5(b) 1H	-
IIIB	9.2-9.9 4H	6.6-8.4 4H	4.1-4.3(b) 4H	3.3-3.7(b) 1H	2.8(s) 6H
IVB	9.2-9.9 4H	6.3-8.5 14H	4.2-4.4(b) 4H	3.5-3.7(b) 1H	-
VB	9.5-9.9 1H	6.6-8.4 8H	4.1-4.3(b) 4H	3.3-3.7(b) 1H	2.8(s) 6H
VIB	9.5-9.9 1H	6.3-8.5 18H	4.2-4.4(b) 4H	3.5-3.7(b) 1H	-
VIIB	9.5-9.6 1H	6.6-8.4 7H	4.1-4.3(b) 4H	3.3-3.7(b) 1H	2.8(s) 6H
VIIIb	9.5-9.6 1H	6.3-8.5 17H	4.2-4.4(b) 4H	3.5-3.7(b) 1H	-

b=broad ; s=singlet.

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